

Report D4.8

“Ontology ecosystem knowledge graph, second version”

Grant Agreement: 958371

Project Title	Ontology-driven data documentation for Industry Commons
Project Acronym	OntoCommons
Project Number	958371
Type of project	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topics	DT-NMBP-39-2020 - Towards Standardised Documentation of Data through taxonomies and ontologies (CSA)
Starting date of Project	01 November 2020
Duration of the project	36 months
Website	www.ontocommons.eu

D4.8

“Ontology ecosystem knowledge graph, second version”

Work Package	WP4 Ontology Commons Ecosystem Toolkit
Task	T4.6 – Knowledge base construction
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Version	Final
Date	25/07/2023

Versioning History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	25/04/2023	Lan Yang	Creation of base version / outline
0.2	14/06/2023	Lan Yang, John Breslin, Christian Kindermann, María Poveda-Villalón	Creation of first version
1.0	26/06/2023	Lan Yang	Update version
final	24/07/2023	Hedi Karray	Technical approval
submission	25/07/2023	Nadja Adamovic	Final approval and submission

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
OCES	Ontology Commons Ecosystem
OCEANS	OntoCommons Collaborative Editing and Authoring Knowledge Graphs
LOT	Linked Open Terms
IAO	Information Artefact Ontology
OWL	Web Ontology Language
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System

Keywords

Ontology; OCEANS; Knowledge base; Knowledge graph

Disclaimer

OntoCommons (958371) is a Coordination & Support Action funded by the European Commission under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Horizon 2020 (H2020). This document contains information on researched by OntoCommons Beneficiaries. Any reference to the content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organization, and publication date. The document was produced with the funding of the European Commission. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the OntoCommons Consortium and cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission. The authors of this document have taken any available measure in order for its content to be accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

Executive Summary

This document provides a comprehensive overview of the OntoCommons project's knowledge base, which is developed through the use of a designated platform called OCEANS (OntoCommons Collaborative Editing and Authoring Knowledge graphs), used to record the knowledge generated in the project in a machine-readable format and visualized through knowledge graphs. The OCEANS platform is built on top of an open-source collaborative environment supporting RDF/OWL known as WebProtégé, which has been customized to better suit the needs of OntoCommons while still retaining most of its features.

The primary objective of creating the knowledge base is to ensure that all the information regarding the Ontology Commons Ecosystem (OCES) Toolkit generated within Work Package 4 (WP4) is encoded into machine-readable knowledge graphs that describe the OCES Toolkit and beyond. This will enable researchers and practitioners from diverse backgrounds to collaborate and contribute to the knowledge base, thereby enriching the OntoCommons project.

The first version of the ontology ecosystem knowledge graph accomplished many valuable outcomes. For instance, it defined the ontology ecosystem knowledge base and knowledge graph, established the content model of the ontology ecosystem knowledge base, analyzed the requirements for the collaborative editing and authoring platform, created the architecture of OCEANS, and generated the first version of the ontology ecosystem knowledge base and knowledge graphs. In the second version, the team focused on restructuring the knowledge base. Specifically, they followed an upper-level ontology, the information artefact ontology, to regroup and classify the information artefacts used in the OCES Toolkit. Additionally, the knowledge graph of the second version was visualized through SousLeSens to enhance the project's cutting-edge nature and ensure it remains at the forefront of the field. This iterative process of refining and enhancing the ontology ecosystem knowledge graph is a continuous effort to improve its functionality and relevance.

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1. Introduction

The OntoCommons project is a collaborative effort aimed at creating an ontology commons ecosystem (OCES) that consists of ontologies, methodologies, tools, references, demonstration cases, and additional sources related to ontologies and their applications. The ecosystem is designed to serve as a foundation for data documentation, annotation, and standardisation in the industrial domain. Throughout the course of the project, a vast amount of information, data, and knowledge is collected and generated. The responsibility of T4.6 is to ensure that all of this information, especially the knowledge describing the OCES Toolkit, is encoded into a knowledge base that organises machine-readable data describing the OCES Toolkit at the meta-level.

To achieve its goal, T4.6 developed two versions of a knowledge graph to represent the OCES Toolkit. The first version of the OCES knowledge graph (D4.5) was generated within the first 12 months of the task duration, with a focus on encoding the specification of the ontology development phases and the descriptions of tools that implement them. The second version (D4.8) updates all amendments to the OCES reference implementation. This version cross-references the ontology development phases defined in D4.2 – Methodological Framework for Ontology Management [Fernández-Izquierdo et al., 2021], the survey results from D4.3 – Landscape Analysis of Ontology Engineering Tools [Skjæveland et al., 2021], and the recommendation for a toolchain covering the components of the OCES Toolkit described in D4.6 – Ontology Ecosystem Reference Implementation [Poveda-Villalón et al., 2022]. The three reference deliverables focus on three different topics. D4.2 introduces the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology, which is the methodological framework for OntoCommons. It describes the activities that should be performed in the ontology development phases. D4.3 provides a landscape analysis of tools for ontology engineering. It details information about each tool and categorizes them by their features. D4.6 recommends a toolchain of stand-alone and online software systems that cover the components of OCES Toolkit and the processes in the proposed methodological framework, which is also known as reference implementation. Finally, in this deliverable, D4.8 formalizes the meta-level knowledge about the methodological framework and the relevant toolchain in a machine-readable, fully interoperable, and standards-compliant knowledge graph.

To develop the knowledge graph, the project has established a platform named OCEANS (OntoCommons Collaborative Editing and Authoring kNowledge graphS). OCEANS is a customised application of a generic web-based RDF/OWL editor, WebProtégé [Tania et al., 2013]. By using OCEANS, the knowledge graph uses RDF/OWL as a representation language and enables the collaborative authoring of the OCES content. One of the main features of OCEANS is that it reuses the functionalities of WebProtégé and provides extensive support for collaboration in the development of knowledge graph content, including change tracking, discussion thread, access control, and visualisation. In addition, the second version of the knowledge graph has been imported into a web-based knowledge graph visualiser called SousLeSens¹. This enables graph visualisation and manipulation in the most effective way to understand their content.

¹ <http://industryportal.enit.fr/souslesens>

This report is a supplementary document to the knowledge graph file. It focuses on the aspects that the knowledge graph file does not specify.

2.Task Overview

T4.6 aims to construct a knowledge base for the OCES Toolkit. The task starts in M12 and continues until the end of the project, divided primarily into two phases: Phase 1, which spans from M12 to M20, and Phase 2, which spans from M21 to M32. The following sections describe the objectives, methodology, and deliverables for the entire task duration, with emphasis on the implementation in the second phase in detail. Achievements in the first phase are detailed in the first report [Breslin and Yang, 2022].

T4.6 is linked to two deliverables: D4.5 – Ontology Ecosystem Knowledge Graph, First Version (due in M20) and D4.8 – Ontology Ecosystem Knowledge Graph, Second Version (due in M32). D4.5 presents a knowledge graph that formally encodes and represents the specification of ontology development phases and guidelines, and maintains formal links with descriptions of tools that implement them. D4.8 deals with any updates to the data schema or amendments to the reference implementation, and provides a report accompanying this deliverable.

Specifically, the task aims to achieve the following targets:

- Describe the LOT methodology of the ontology development phases in the form of a knowledge graph.
- Include details of existing ontology engineering tools collected from landscape analysis into the knowledge base, making them indexable and readable by both humans and machines.
- Map the ontology development phases and the existing ontology engineering tools.
- Establish a mechanism to ensure the content of the knowledge graph can be continuously updated with the progress of the project.
- Introduce a tool in the knowledge base construction to support configuration management between various incremental revisions.
- Create a tunnel for all project participants to collaboratively contribute to the editing and authoring of the knowledge graph.
- Display the knowledge base in the form of a visualized graph.
- Publish the knowledge graph so that the public can view and understand the meta-level description of the ontology ecosystem.

The first phase (M12 – M20) of T4.6 primarily focuses on creating the content of the methodological framework and reviewing the existing ontology engineering tools. The updates of a toolchain for the OCES Toolkit, amendments from the demonstration's feedback loop, and any other revisions of the reference implementation are added in the second phase (M21 – M32).

3. Introduction to Ontology Ecosystem Knowledge Graph, Second Version

The second version of the ontology ecosystem knowledge graph is an important development in the field of semantic web technologies. Maintained by OCEANS² and accessible via its GitHub repository³, the knowledge graph is an invaluable resource for researchers and practitioners alike. In order to view the knowledge graph, users need to need to login with the following account credentials, username: viewer, password: viewer, for OCEANS.

In the following, we will demonstrate how to read and use the information contained in the knowledge graph. The information regarding the OCES Toolkit is classified according to an upper level ontology, namely the information artefact ontology (IAO)⁴. Alignment as such is a key aspect of the OCES. By leveraging this ontology, users can easily locate not only the OCES methodological framework, which is essential for understanding the process of ontology engineering, but also other important components such as the ontology engineering toolchain.

The OCES methodological framework is located at entity > occurrent > process > planned process > OCES methodological framework in the IAO class hierarchy (shown in Figure 1). It contains the five phases of ontology engineering described by the LOT methodology as well as the corresponding activities.

² <http://srvgal91.deri.ie:8001/>

³ <https://github.com/ontology-ecosystem/knowledge-graph>

⁴ <http://industryportal.enit.fr/ontologies/IAO>

Figure 1 Navigating 'OCES methodological framework' in OCEANS

Let us consider the activity of 'ontology conceptualization', as illustrated in Figure 2. By clicking on a particular class from the class hierarchy, such as 'ontology conceptualization', users can access detailed annotations and relationships that provide a richer context for the concept. This feature enhances the user experience by allowing them to explore the knowledge graph in more detail and gain a more comprehensive understanding of the OCES Toolkit.

Figure 2 Viewing class annotations and relationships in OCEANS, example of 'ontology conceptualization'

In Figure 2 we can see that the activity of 'ontology conceptualization' serves the purpose of creating a model that accurately represents the domain of the ontology, which is an essential part of the ontology implementation phase. The aim of this process is to provide a clear and comprehensive representation of a specific domain, which can be used as a reference for future analysis and development. The output of ontology conceptualization is called 'ontology model', which is a detailed representation of the ontology. It contains all the necessary information about the ontology and its domain, including the relationships and properties of different concepts. By clicking on the jump arrow next to 'ontology model', users can view a detailed description of the model as shown in Figure 3.

The screenshot shows the 'Ontology Commons EcoSystem V2' interface. The left pane displays a 'Class Hierarchy' tree where 'ontology model' is selected and highlighted in blue. The right pane shows the details for the 'ontology model' class, including its IRI, annotations, parents, and relationships.

Class Hierarchy (Left Pane):

- owl:Thing
 - ObsoleteClass
 - entity
 - continuant
 - generically dependent continuant
 - information content entity
 - code set
 - data item
 - datum label
 - directive information entity
 - action specification
 - conditional specification
 - data format specification
 - objective specification
 - plan specification
 - Postal delivery route
 - algorithm
 - programming language
 - software
 - evaluated ontology [9]
 - online ontology [12]
 - ontology model [7]**
 - ontology release candidate [10]
 - software application
 - ontology engineering tool
 - tools for evaluation and validation
 - constraints validator
 - data FAIR validator
 - ontology FAIR validator
 - tools for implementation
 - tools for maintenance
 - tools for project management, version management and issue tracking
 - tools for publication
 - tools for requirement specification
 - tools for specific purposes, not elsewhere classified
 - tools for use

Class: ontology model (Right Pane):

- IRI:** <http://ontocommons.eu/R9kGYTITxMWz4EORpboJI6>
- Annotations:**
 - rdfs:label: ontology model en
- Parents:**
 - software
- Relationships:**
 - is_specified_input_of: ontology encoding
 - is_specified_input_of: ontology reuse

Figure 3 Viewing class annotations and relationships in OCEANS, example of 'ontology model'

The relationships of the 'ontology model' serve as inputs for both 'ontology encoding' and 'ontology reuse' activities. The tag '[7]' next to 'ontology model' on the class hierarchy is the original label in the LOT methodology for 'ontology model'. Furthermore, 'ontology model' is classified under the class 'software', which has siblings such as 'evaluated ontology' (originally marked as [9] in LOT methodology), 'online ontology' (originally marked as [12] in LOT methodology), and 'ontology release candidate' (originally marked as [10] in LOT methodology). It is also worth noting that 'online ontology' has a sibling, 'software application', which is also classified under the class of 'software' (as shown in Figure 3). It contains the ontology engineering tool categories defined in the OCES reference implementation, including

- tools for evaluation and validation,
- tools for implementation,
- tools for maintenance,
- tools for project management, version management and issue tracking,
- tools for publication,
- tools for requirement specification,
- tools for specific purposes, not elsewhere classified, and

- tools for use.

Each tool category has been further divided according to the functions of the tools. For example, 'tools for evaluation and validation' include 'constraints validator', 'data FAIR validator' and 'ontology FAIR validator'.

When using the 'ontology FAIR validator' (shown in Figure 4), users can assess the FAIR level of an ontology or to what extent the FAIR principles are being met. This is an important step in the 'online publication' activity, which is one of the many phases of ontology engineering. By providing this mapping between ontology engineering tools and phases, the OCEANS reference implementation has become an essential reference for ontology developers.

The screenshot shows the 'Ontology Commons EcoSystem V2' interface. On the left, a 'Class Hierarchy' tree is displayed, with 'ontology FAIR validator' selected. The right panel shows the details for this class, including its IRI, annotations, parents, and relationships.

Class: ontology FAIR validator

IRI
http://ontocommons.eu/Rcx9TTNGJrs4YqwOBdx8s7

Annotations

| | | |
|----------------|---|----|
| rdfs:label | ontology FAIR validator | en |
| dc:description | These systems assess the FAIR level of an ontology or to what extends the FAIR principles are meet. | en |

Parents

- tools for evaluation and validation

Relationships

- participates in: online publication

Figure 4 Viewing class annotations and relationships in OCEANS, example of 'ontology FAIR validator'

In order to find out what ontology FAIR validators exist, users can use the 'Query' Tab provided by OCEANS to inquire about relevant information in the knowledge base. This tool makes it easy for users to discover the available options for ontology FAIR validation. Figure 5 shows the results of an enquiry about 'what are the available ontology FAIR validators?' This feature highlights the user-friendly nature of OCEANS and its ability to support ontology development in a comprehensive and accessible way.

Figure 5 Query in OCEANS, example of 'ontology FAIR validator'

Up until this point, the knowledge graph has been successfully integrated into the OCES methodological framework and the OCES reference implementation. This is a significant accomplishment, as it represents a crucial step towards the completion of the OCES Toolkit, which will provide a comprehensive toolchain for ontology engineering. It is important to note that the integration of the knowledge graph is a critical component of this process, as it allows for the seamless documentation of the entire workflow. With this new addition, the OCES Toolkit will undoubtedly become an essential resource for anyone involved in ontology engineering.

4. Visualisation of Ontology Ecosystem Knowledge Graph through SousLeSens

SousLeSens is a powerful suite of open source tools that provides an array of functionalities to enhance SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) vocabularies and OWL ontologies. The tool offers a wide range of capabilities including navigating, comparing, visualizing, and enriching vocabularies and ontologies. With support for knowledge graph representations and queries, SousLeSens enables users to perform a variety of tasks such as generating and managing triple stores. Additionally, it employs a flexible and sustainable information methodology that adheres to standard frameworks, making it an essential tool for ontology and knowledge graph visualization.

The name 'SousleSens' is derived from the French expression 'cela tombe sous le sens,' which means 'it is obvious, or it should be, if not yet.' This name represents the tool's intuitive and user-friendly interface, which allows users to easily navigate and understand the vast amount of data contained within. Moreover, SousLeSens is an essential tool for various industries as it provides a comprehensive and efficient solution for data management and analysis. With its powerful

6. References

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